

**A STUDY ON THE EFFECT OF PRACTICES FOLLOWED BY IT COMPANIES ON
FACTORS INFLUENCING THE WORK-LIFE BALANCE OF WOMEN
EMPLOYEES IN BENGALURU CITY**

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Abstract:

Purpose:

The paper analyzes the effect of practices followed by IT companies on the factors influencing women employees work life balance at Bengaluru City.

Design/Methodology/Approach:

Data were collected through the questionnaire using convenience sampling. The survey questionnaire covered various domains, including factors affecting the work life balance of women employees and the effect of practices followed by IT companies on the factors influencing work life balance. The study employed a sample consisting of 512 women employees from IT companies located at Bengaluru. Data analysis has done using simple linear regression tests using SPSS to assess the data.

Findings:

The results reveals that there is a significant relationship between the effect of practices followed by IT companies has significant influence on factors influencing women employees work life balance.

This analysis reveals how practices followed by IT companies influence the factors influencing work-life balance related variables of work environment, job satisfaction and quality of life. Three components were scored on a five-point Likert scale for reliability.

Key Words:

Practices followed, IT companies, factors, women employees and work-life balance

1. INTRODUCTION:

Work-life balance, or WLB, is the smooth integration of work and life. The need for multiple earners is growing as a result of rising education costs, increased service options, and rising living expenses. Because of technological advancements, globalization, and increased career options, the desire for empowerment is growing every day. Women are now much more devoted to their families, and as their careers have advanced, they have begun providing financial support for their well-being.

Work life balance, in its broadest sense, is defined as a satisfactory level of involvement or 'fit' between the multiple roles in a person's life (Hudson, 2005). In order to define the harmony between a person's professional and personal life, the phrase "work-life balance" is often employed. It is widely acknowledged that achieving a work-life balance is crucial for a person's psychological health and that signs of a successful balance between work and family responsibilities include strong self-esteem, satisfaction, and a general sense of harmony in one's life.

Every profession has stress, workload, work pressure and unsatisfied employees but the percentage is very high in service-oriented industries like Information Technology. The Information Technology (IT) industry has become the most robust industries in the world. IT, more than any other industry or economic facet, has an increased productivity, particularly in the developed world, and therefore is a key driver of global economic growth. Owing to its easy accessibility and the wide range of IT products available, the demand for IT services has increased substantially over the years.

The existing study highlights the direct link between practices followed by IT companies and the factors influencing women employees work life balance at Bengaluru City. The study includes following key research questions:

RQ1: What are the practices followed by IT companies for women employees work life balance?

RQ2: How the practices followed by IT companies affect the factors influencing women employees work life balance.

The remainder of this research paper is structured as follows: With a review of significant literature and the creation of hypotheses, the second section discusses practices followed by IT companies and its effect on factors influencing women employees work life balance. Data analysis is covered in the third section and discussion of the findings and their implications is

covered in the fifth section. The study is concluded in the final section, along with recommendations for further research.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW:

Ms. Chanda Kochhar, MD & CEO, ICICI Bank said (International Women's Day): 'Although women form 48% of the population in our country, their representation in the workforce is much lower than men. Many women who join the workforce are sometimes forced to take a break or even leave their jobs, due to various life stage needs like maternity and child care. Lack of support system due to predominance of nuclear families, inadequate infrastructural facilities like crèches and long commute time further accentuates the problem. To ensure that the working women do not leave the workforce, there is a strong need for a robust support system, both at home and at work.

(Dipak Mishra, 2023), in their research revealed that human resources play a significant role in encouraging a healthy work-life balance, especially in international settings where workers' expectations and values may vary. Flexible work schedules, employee support programs, and open lines of communication are just some of the HR practices like these that were singled out in the report as having a positive impact on work- life balance. The research fills a gap in the literature by examining how human resources may help employees achieve work-life harmony in a variety of cultural settings.

(Oyewobi, 2022), in their study investigated the relationship between work-life policies (WLPs) and organizational commitment, focusing on female construction professionals in Nigeria. It also explores whether work-life balance (WLB) mediators in this relationship. The results show that because WLB partially mediates the relationship between WLPs and organizational commitment, it increases positive organizational commitment. This study makes a valuable contribution by giving managers and staff members the chance to comprehend the importance of offering WLPs, which will allow workers to manage their work and family obligations and ultimately boost organizational commitment.

(Barck-Holst, 2022), they discussed how practice of working less hours led to a better work-life balance, which in turn improved mood. This was probably due to having more control over the demands of one's personal life, which allowed for a more diversified and improved recovery and more access to informal social support. The interviewees recommend a procedure for creating and preserving a healthy work-life balance.

(Mahi Uddin, 2021), in their article said that the effects of coworkers' and managers' emotional and practical assistance on female bank employees' ability to balance work and personal obligations. According to the study, the work-life balance (WLB) is significantly impacted by both the emotional support received from coworkers and the practical and emotional assistance received from supervisors. Additionally, the results showed that emotional support from supervisors had a greater impact on the WLB than did emotional support from coworkers. The results, however, demonstrated the minimal impact of instrumental assistance from teammates.

(Koon, 2020), in his study examine how work-life balance (WLB) practices applied at the organizational level associate with WLB practices and performance appraisal at the individual level that affects employee commitment, underpinned by the theory of supportiveness and the relational perspective. Results indicate that the consistency of employee perception of WLB practices and performance appraisal at individual level influence employee commitment, whereas WLB practices at the organization level have a negative influence on employee commitment.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- a. To reveal the practices followed by IT companies towards women employees work life balance at Bengaluru city.
- b. To understand the effect of practices followed by IT companies on factors influencing work life balance of women employees.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

4.1 Type of research:

The descriptive research and exploratory research type have been used in this study. The descriptive research design component focuses specifically on analyzing the attitude and perception of women IT employees. Attitude means the how women employees in IT companies feels work life balance and its issues. The exploratory research design, on the other hand, delves deeper into understanding the various factors that influence work-life balance among the sample population.

4.2 Data Collection

Primary data is original information collected directly by a researcher; these were used for the study to draw first-hand information and insights regarding women employees' perceptions towards work life balance and strategies followed by them to maintain WLB.

4.3 Sampling Techniques:

The study concentrated on large IT firms located in Bengaluru's well-known technology parks, including Electronic City, ITPL, Global Village Tech Park, Manyata Embassy Business Park, and Infosys, Wipro, TCS, Capgemini, and Cognizant, among others. However, the stringent corporate HR practices and data privacy regulations that many of these firms uphold made it difficult to gain accurate demographic data and direct access to female employees. Through professional networking sites, recommendations from other participants, or lunchtime interactions at food courts, the researcher has made contact with female IT professionals.

4.4 Sample Size:

The sample size for this study was determined based on power analysis using G*Power software (Faul et al., 2007). For a power of 0.95 with a 0.05 level of significance and 0.50 population size (when population size is not sure), the minimum sample size requirement was 385. A sample of 512 women employees was drawn from the total population women employees.

4.5 Statistical Tools Used:

1. The descriptive statistics frequencies, percentages, minimum, maximum mean and standard deviation are obtained.
2. Simple linear regression was carried out to see the practices followed by IT companies and its significant influence on factors significantly influencing the work life balance related to the variables work environment, job satisfaction and quality of life.

4.6 Hypotheses Development:

1) **H01:**There is no significant relationship between practices followed by IT companies and factors influencing work life balance.

Ha1:There is significant relationship between practices followed by IT companies and factors influencing work life balance.

2) **H02:** There is no significant relationship between practices followed and work environment related factors influencing WLB.

Ha2:There is significant relationship between practices followed and work environment related factors influencing WLB.

3) **H03:**There is no significant relationship between practices followed and job satisfaction related factors influencing WLB.

Ha3:There is significant relationship between practices followed and job satisfaction related factors influencing WLB.

4) **H04:**There is no significant relationship between practices followed and quality of life related factors influencing WLB.

Ha4:There is significant relationship between practices followed and quality of life related factors influencing WLB.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

5.1 Opinion towards practices followed by IT companies

Table 1: Summary of opinion towards practices followed by IT companies in managing the work life balance for women employees: Counts and Percentages.

Sl. No.	Questions	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
1	Always working with proper planning	7(1.3%)	21(4.1%)	88(17.1%)	237(46.2%)	159(31%)	512
2	Company facilitating taking care of paid vacation	13(2.5%)	30(5.8%)	97(18.9%)	232(45.3%)	140(27.3%)	512
3	Policies favoring to encash of earned leave	13(2.5%)	29(5.6%)	103(20.1%)	236(46.0%)	131(25.5%)	512
4	Providing health care insurance facilities for employee and her family	9(1.7%)	21(4.1%)	86(16.7%)	240(46.8%)	156(30.4%)	512
5	Facilities for taking maternity leaves	7(1.3%)	23(4.4%)	107(20.8%)	237(46.2%)	138(26.9%)	512
6	Facilities for child care taking at	14(2.7%)	42(8.2%)	116(22.6%)	215(41.9%)	125(24.4%)	512

	work place.			(%))	(%)	
7	Companies are providing relaxation techniques for employees like – Yoga, meditation and out bound programme	10(1.9%)	33(6.4%)	113(22%)	229(44.7%)	127(24.8%)	512
8	Policies supporting for personnel problem solving	10(1.9%)	26(5%)	103(20.1%)	239(46.6%)	134(26.1%)	512
9	Facilities regarding flexible timings at workplace.	9(1.7%)	24(4.6%)	100(19.5%)	239(46.6%)	140(27.3%)	512
10	Allowing work from home options in difficult time	5(0.9%)	22(4.2%)	97(18.9%)	242(47.2%)	146(28.5%)	512
11	Encouraging personal growth – skills and hobbies	5(0.9%)	22(4.2%)	97(18.9%)	242(47.2%)	146(28.5%)	512
12	Encouraging healthy lifestyle	9(1.7%)	28(5.4%)	95(18.5%)	247(48.2%)	133(25.9%)	512
13	Company making facilities of availabilities of hygienic food at work place	7(1.3%)	25(4.8%)	110(21.4%)	235(45.8%)	135(26.3%)	512
14	Company providing healthy and safe environment for women employees	8(1.5%)	25(4.8%)	91(17.7%)	243(47.4%)	145(28.3%)	512
15	Providing safe transportation facilities to women employees	8(1.5%)	27(5.2%)	97(18.9%)	247(48.2%)	133(25.9%)	512
16	Company provides loan facilities to women employees to support their family financial problems.	12(2.3%)	34(6.6%)	104(20.3%)	232(45.3%)	130(25.3%)	512
17	Company should support of Women Empowerment issues.	6(1.1%)	27(5.2%)	94(18.3%)	245(47.8%)	140(27.3%)	512
18	Company should provide counselling and legal assistance to women employees as a part of safety at work place.	10(1.9%)	28(5.4%)	113(22%)	233(45.5%)	128(25%)	512

According to the above table, female employees have a very favourable opinion for the organization's support for welfare programs and work-life balance. The vast majority of respondents—typically more than 70% combined—fall into the "Agree" and "Strongly Agree" categories across all 18 questions. Proper work planning, paid time off, leave encashment policies, health insurance, maternity benefits, and flexible work arrangements including work-from-home possibilities are especially valued by employees. Although childcare facilities exhibit somewhat greater levels of neutrality and disagreement when compared to other characteristics, supportive practices such as childcare facilities, relaxation

programs (yoga and meditation), and help with personal problem-solving are also evaluated favourably. Organizations are also seen as encouraging personal development, healthy lifestyles, the availability of clean food, and safe workplaces, including facilities for women's mobility. Financial support via loans and help or women empowerment initiatives, counselling, and legal assistance are also positively acknowledged.

Overall, the results show that Bengaluru's IT firms are working hard to establish a safe, encouraging, and employee-friendly workplace, however some aspects, like childcare provision, might still need improvement.

5.2 Opinion towards factors that influence women employee's work life balance

Table 2: Summary of significance of Work Environment: Counts and Percentages

S. No.	Questions	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
1	Quality of work	5(0.9%)	15(2.9%)	86(16.8%)	256(50%)	150(29.3%)	512
2	Pay and Benefits (paid time-offs)	8(1.5%)	22(4.2%)	102(19.9%)	230(44.9%)	150(29.3%)	512
3	Career breaks / Sabbaticals	3(0.5%)	6(5.0%)	116(22.6%)	233(45.50%)	134(26.1%)	512
4	Flexible working hours	6(1.1%)	22(4.2%)	100(19.5%)	239(46.6%)	145(28.3%)	512
5	Opportunities for career growth	4(0.7%)	16(3.1%)	99(19.3%)	248(48.4%)	145(28.3%)	512
6	Support during maternity and postpartum	2(0.3%)	17(3.3%)	106(20.7%)	238(46.4%)	149(29.1%)	512
7	Conductive/ Supportive work environment	5(0.9%)	22(4.2%)	98(19.1%)	243(47.4%)	144(28.1%)	512
8	Insurance plans for self and family	7(1.3%)	17(3.3%)	89(17.3%)	250(48.8%)	149(29.1%)	512

The answers show that female employees have a very favourable opinion of workplace elements affecting work-life balance. The vast majority of respondents fall into the "Agree" and "Strongly Agree" categories in every category, especially when it comes to prospects for career advancement, flexible work schedules, compensation and benefits, and work quality. Additionally, workers are quite satisfied with the organization's maternity support, the

availability of personal and family insurance, and the encouraging work atmosphere. Overall results indicate that firms are successfully addressing important variables that lead to employee well-being and professional development, even though a moderate percentage of respondents are neutral about career breaks and sabbaticals.

Table 3: Summary of opinion towards the job satisfaction level: *Counts and Percentages.*

Sl. No.	Questions	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
1	Satisfied with the growth and developmental opportunities provided	4(2.7%)	29(5.0%)	99(19.3%)	234(45.7%)	139(27.1%)	512
2	Satisfied with the work loads	15(2.9%)	32(6.2%)	106(20.7%)	232(45.3%)	127(24.8%)	512
3	Do you think your contributions are recognized	17(3.3%)	32(6.2%)	113(22.1%)	222(43.3%)	128(25%)	512
4	Lack of recognition for the hard work and effort	13(2.5%)	63(12.3%)	135(26.3%)	191(37.3%)	110(21.4%)	512
5	Do you feel connected to your co-workers?	10(1.9%)	26(5.0%)	115(22.4%)	221(43.1%)	140(27.3%)	512

The findings show a generally positive level of satisfaction among employees regarding workplace experiences. A majority of respondents express satisfaction with growth and development opportunities, manageable workloads, recognition of contributions, and a sense of connection with co-workers, as reflected by high “Agree” and “Strongly Agree” responses. However, there is a comparatively higher level of neutrality and some disagreement regarding recognition, particularly concerning lack of acknowledgment for hard work and effort. Overall, while employees perceive the work environment as supportive and engaging, recognition practices appear to be an area that may need further improvement.

Table 4: Summary of opinion towards work life balance and quality of life/satisfaction: *Counts and Percentages.*

Sl. No.	Questions	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Total
1	I am satisfied with my free and leisure hours	13(2.5%)	34(6.6%)	91(17.7%)	240(46.8%)	134(26.1%)	512
2	I take my breakfast in the morning without any hurry	17(3.3%)	41(8%)	99(19.3%)	224(43.7%)	131(25.5%)	512
3	I am satisfied with the family trips I enjoy during vacation at	12(2.3%)	33(6.4%)	93(18.1%)	236(46.0%)	138(26.9%)	512

	least once in a year))	
4	I am satisfied with my weekend shopping and outing with my family	10(1.9%)	23(4.4%)	110(21.4%))	223(43.5%))	146(28.5%))	512
5	I am satisfied about spending quality time for myself	15(2.9%)	40(7.8%)	111(21.6%))	225(43.9%))	121(23.6%))	512
6	I am satisfied about spending quality time with my family and siblings.	10(1.9%)	34(6.6%)	103(20.1%))	234(45.7%))	131(25.5%))	512
7	I am satisfied with my engagements in social activities I participate in a week day and weekends.	11(2.1%)	39(7.6%)	107(20.8%))	221(43.1%))	134(26.1%))	512
8	I am satisfied with my regular contacts with relatives and friends.	10(1.9%)	26(5%)	103 (20.1%)	239(46.6%))	134(26.1%))	512

The findings show that employees are generally quite satisfied with their personal and family lives. Across all assertions, the majority of respondents fell into the "Agree" and "Strongly Agree" categories, indicating that the majority of workers are content with their free time, relationships with family, vacations, weekend getaways, and social engagements. They also give favourable reports about handling everyday routines, such as eating breakfast without rushing, and keeping in touch with friends and family on a regular basis. However, a considerable percentage of neutral and some disagreement responses—especially in areas like social activities and personal time—indicate that some employees still struggle to strike the perfect work-life balance. Overall, the results show that employees' perceptions of their personal life satisfaction are positive although somewhat inconsistent.

Table 5: Effect of Practices Followed on Factors Influencing Women Employee Work Life Balance

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	R Value	F	df (Regression, Residual)	Coefficient Value (a,b)	t	p value	Significance
Practices Followed	Work Environment	0.55	224.16	1	18.68	13.20	0.000**	<0.01
				510	0.30	14.97	0.000**	<0.01
	Job Satisfaction	0.59	276.74	1	5.69	6.98	0.000**	<0.01
				510	0.19	16.64	0.000**	<0.01
	Quality	0.73	575.43	1	3.88	3.39	0.001**	<0.01
				510	0.39	23.99	0.000**	<0.01
*pvalue<0.05** p value<0.01								

The results of the regression analysis show that all three dependent variables—work atmosphere, job satisfaction, and quality—are significantly impacted by the practices used. Moderate to strong positive associations are indicated by the correlation values ($R = 0.55$, 0.59 , and 0.73 , respectively), with quality showing the highest effect. The overall model relevance is confirmed by the strong F-values for each model. With p-values less than 0.01 in every instance, both regression coefficients and t-values are significant and statistically significant, providing compelling evidence against the null hypothesis. This suggests that organizational practices are essential for improving the workplace, raising worker satisfaction, and producing higher-quality results, with a particularly noticeable impact on quality.

Hypothesis	Result	Remark
H0 1: There is no significant relationship between practices followed by IT companies and factors influencing work life balance.	The result has disclosed that there is a significant relationship between practices followed by IT companies on variables of work life balance of women employees with $p \text{ value} < 0.01$.	Rejected
H0 2: There is no significant relationship between practices followed and work environment related factors influencing WLB.	The study has disclosed that there is a significant relationship between practices followed and work environment related factors influencing WLB with $p \text{ value} < 0.01$.	Rejected
H03: There is no significant relationship between practices followed and job satisfaction related factors influencing WLB.	The result has disclosed that there is a significant relationship between practices followed and job satisfaction related factors influencing WLB with $p \text{ value} < 0.01$.	Rejected
H04: There is no significant relationship between practices followed and quality of life related factors influencing WLB.	The result has revealed that there is a significant relationship between practices followed and quality of life factors influencing WLB with $p \text{ value} < 0.01$.	Rejected

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS.

The overall analysis of the data indicates that women employees in IT companies experience a largely positive and supportive work environment, with organizational practices playing a significant role in shaping their work-life balance, job satisfaction, and overall well-being. A substantial majority of respondents consistently expressed agreement across factors such as proper planning, paid leave, health insurance, maternity support, flexible working hours, work-from-home options, and safe workplace facilities. Organizations are also perceived to actively promote personal growth, healthy lifestyles, and employee welfare initiatives, although areas like childcare facilities and recognition for hard work show relatively higher neutrality and scope for improvement.

Employees report high satisfaction with key job-related aspects including quality of work, pay and benefits, career growth opportunities, and supportive work environments. Similarly, personal life indicators such as leisure time, family interactions, vacations, and social engagement also reflect favorable responses, suggesting a reasonably balanced integration of work and personal life. However, some employees experience moderate challenges in maintaining personal time and receiving adequate recognition.

The regression analysis further strengthens these findings by demonstrating that organizational practices have a statistically significant and positive impact on work environment, job satisfaction, and quality, with the strongest influence observed on quality outcomes.

In conclusion, IT companies in Bengaluru are largely successful in fostering a conducive and employee-friendly ecosystem that supports women employees both professionally and personally. Nevertheless, enhancing recognition systems, childcare support, and certain aspects of work-life balance could further improve employee satisfaction and organizational effectiveness.

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